

Solution study of ternary systems involving transition metals, dipeptide and catecholic ligands

Seema Kumari Yadav, Neerja Upadhayaya (Dwivedi), R. Nair (Ahuja)^a and K. Dwivedi*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : seema_chem@rediffmail.com

^aVijaya Rajee Govt. Girls P.G. College, Morar, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 08 June 2010, revised 08 March 2011, accepted 09 March 2011

Abstract : Glycylglycine (Glygly), L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (DOPA) and L-tyrosine (Tyr) are three important ligands in biological systems. In order to draw inference on their complexation behaviour, solution studies in mixed ligand systems involving these ligands with Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cd^{II} have been carried out using pH-metric titration technique, in aqueous medium at three different ionic strengths ($\mu = 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 M$) and at two different temperatures 20 °C and 30 °C. SCOGS computer program was applied for computation. Protonated and non-protonated mixed ligand complexes are inferred to be formed through multiple equilibria. Distribution of various species is presented in the form of speciation curves. The two ligands are coordinated to the metal ion simultaneously in a single step. $\Delta \log K$ values support the formation of ternary complexes.

Keywords : Ternary complexes, protonated species, non-protonated species.

Introduction

The results of the investigation of multiple equilibria involving dipeptides ligand have contributed in understanding the mode of complexation of these ligands in biological systems¹⁻⁵. There is lot more scope for exploring the related equilibria. In continuation to our work on equilibrium studies involving catechols⁶, the present paper incorporates the results of mixed ligand systems of Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cd^{II} with Glygly-Tyr and Glygly-DOPA where Glygly = glycylglycine, Tyr = L-tyrosine and DOPA = L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine. The chosen ligands bear immense biological and medicinal importance.

Results and discussion

The dissociation constants of Glygly, Tyr and DOPA are in close agreement with the literature values⁷. The values of the formation constants of binary and ternary complexes of M^{II} (where M^{II} = Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cd^{II}) with glycylglycine, Tyr and DOPA are also obtained under the identical sets of experimental conditions. Formation of ternary complexes in M^{II}-ligand 'A'-ligand 'B' system (where ligand 'A' = Glygly and ligand 'B' = DOPA/Tyr) was predicted on the basis of titration curves obtained by plotting pH against volume of alkali added.

Representative curves are shown in Fig. 1'a'. In Fig. 1a is the moles of alkali added per mole of metal/ligand. It is

Fig. 1. pH vs volume of NaOH (mL) curves for (a) Ni^{II}-Glygly-DOPA, (b) Ni^{II}-Glygly-Tyr (1 : 1 : 1) systems at 30 °C ($\mu = 0.10 M$ (NaNO₃)) : Curve (1) represents acid titration curve, (2) ligand 'A' (Glygly) titration curve, (3) ligand 'B' (DOPA/Tyr) titration curve, (4) metal-ligand 'A' (1 : 1) titration curve, (5) metal-ligand 'B' (1 : 1) titration curve, (6) mixed-ligand (1 : 1 : 1) titration curve and (T) theoretical composite curve.

observed that mixed ligand titration curves are displaced to the right side of the theoretical composite curves 'T', the latter being obtained by the theoretical addition of the values of 'a' corresponding to ligand titration curves of one ligand to the metal-ligand (1 : 1) titration curve of other ligand, thereby strongly supporting the formation of mixed ligand complexes.

By the analysis of titration curves it is concluded that the two ligands are co-ordinated to metal ion simultaneously in a single step. The qualitative analysis of experimental data is subjected to computation in accordance to the algebraic method of Chaberek and Martell^{8,9} as modified by Dey *et al.*¹⁰. It is further refined by SCOGS computer program^{11,12}.

The values of dissociation constants of all the ligands are given in Table 1. The formation constants of the 1 : 1 binary species are given in Table 2, whereas the formation constants of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary species along with free energy change ΔG° are given in Tables 3 and 4. The values of formation constants of ternary complexes are much higher as compared to the binary complexes. This is apparent from the $\Delta \log K (= \log \beta_{MAB} - \log \beta_{MA} - \log \beta_{MB})$ values obtained by difference of the thermodynamic stability constant of ternary complexes and simple

Table 1. Dissociation constants of ligands ($\log \beta_{\mu} \rightarrow 0$)

Parameter	Glygly		DOPA		Tyr	
	20 °C	30 °C	20 °C	30 °C	20 °C	30 °C
$\log \beta_{HA}$	8.3	7.75	13.21	13.01	10.01	9.81
$\log \beta_{H_2A}$	-	-	21.88	21.75	17.79	17.85
$\log \beta_{H_3A}$	-	-	30.98	30.81	-	-

Table 3. Thermodynamic stability constants of diprotonated M^{II} -Glygly-DOPA ternary complexes in equimolar systems along with $\Delta \log K$ values

System	20°C			30°C		
	$\log K_{(\mu \rightarrow 0)}$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta \log K$	$\log K_{(\mu \rightarrow 0)}$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta \log K$
$\log \beta_{NiH_2AB}$	32.65	183.1	-0.32	31.98	185.5	-0.74
$\log K_{NiH_2AB}$	10.95	61.43	-	10.79	62.59	-
$\log \beta_{CoH_2AB}$	31.68	177.7	0.16	30.78	178.5	0.22
$\log K_{CoH_2AB}$	11.03	61.87	-	10.74	62.30	-
$\log \beta_{CdH_2AB}$	30.98	173.8	0.14	30.09	174.5	-0.26
$\log K_{CdH_2AB}$	10.91	61.2	-	10.71	62.13	-

Thermodynamic formation constants were obtained by extrapolating the $\log \beta$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plot to zero ionic strength.

Table 2. Thermodynamic formation constants of binary complexes of M^{II} in equimolar systems

Parameter	Ni ^{II}		Co ^{II}		Cd ^{II}	
	20 °C	30 °C	20 °C	30 °C	20 °C	30 °C
$\log \beta_{MGlygly}$	5.39	5.33	4.25	3.78	4.09	3.69
$\log \beta_{MH_2DOPA}$	27.58	27.39	27.27	26.78	26.75	26.66
$\log K_{MH_2DOPA}$	5.78	5.64	5.57	4.75	5.83	5.77
$\log \beta_{MHTyr}$	14.32	14.12	12.39	12.13	12.68	12.29
$\log \beta_{MTyr}$	6.15	5.91	4.75	4.62	4.52	4.28
$\log K_{MHTyr}$	5.84	5.82	4.7	4.52	4.12	3.89

Thermodynamic formation constants were obtained by extrapolating the $\log \beta$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plot to zero ionic strength.

binary complexes, thereby supporting the formation of ternary complexes.

Mixed ligand complexes of stoichiometry $MABH_2$, $MABH$, MAB have been assumed in different equilibria. It is observed that in the ternary systems involving Tyr as ligand 'B' the formation of monoprotonated species of the type $MABH$ is predominant which is further deprotonated to form MAB . Whereas in the case of ternary complexes of DOPA as ligand 'B' the formation of $MABH_2$ as major species is concluded. This can be attributed to additional hydroxyl group in DOPA as compared to Tyr. Further dissociation of $MABH_2$ species which can lead to formation of $MABH/MAB$ species at higher pH could not be revealed because of formation of polymeric species¹³.

Speciation curves for various species of M^{II} -ligand 'A'-ligand 'B' (where $M^{II} = Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II}$ and ligand 'A' = Glygly, ligand 'B' = DOPA) are given in Fig. 2. It can be observed from the curves that $MABH_2$ species

Table 4. Thermodynamic stability constants of monoprotonated and nonprotonated M^{II} -Glygly 'A'-Tyr 'B' ternary complexes in equimolar systems along with $\Delta \log K$ values

System	20 °C			30 °C		
	$\log K_{(\mu \rightarrow 0)}$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta \log K$	$\log K_{(\mu \rightarrow 0)}$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta \log K$
$\log \beta_{NiHAB}$	18.15	101.8	-	17.89	103.7	-
$\log \beta_{NiAB}$	10.37	58.17	-1.17	10.04	58.24	-1.2
$\log K_{NiHAB}$	10.17	57.05	-	9.86	57.2	-
$\log \beta_{CoHAB}$	18.23	102.2	-	17.79	103.21	-
$\log \beta_{CoAB}$	9.52	53.4	0.52	9.30	53.95	0.9
$\log K_{CoHAB}$	9.07	50.88	-	8.81	51.11	-
$\log \beta_{CdHAB}$	17.98	100.8	-	17.52	101.64	-
$\log \beta_{CdAB}$	9.07	50.88	0.46	8.78	50.93	0.81
$\log K_{CdHAB}$	7.98	44.76	-	7.78	45.13	-

Thermodynamic formation constants were obtained by extrapolating the $\log \beta$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plot to zero ionic strength.

Fig. 2. Speciation curves for (a) Ni^{II} -Glygly-DOPA, (b) Co^{II} -Glygly-DOPA and (c) Cd^{II} -Glygly-DOPA (1 : 1 : 1) systems at 30 °C ($\mu = 0.10 M$ ($NaNO_3$)) : Curve 1 : [M]; (2) [MA]; (3) [MBH_2]; (4) [$MABH_2$].

comes into existence from pH ~ 6.0, then its concentration increases continuously and becomes maximum at pH

~7.8. All calculations for the system involving DOPA are confined below pH 8.5 to avoid errors due to formation of polymeric species at higher pH. Therefore dissociation of protonated species was not considered.

Similarly, speciation curves for all the protonated and non-protonated species of M^{II} -ligand 'A'-ligand 'B' (where $M^{II} = Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II}$ and ligand 'A' = Glygly, ligand 'B' = Tyr) are given in Fig. 3. These curves show that MABH species comes into existence from pH ~ 6.0 and its concentration become maximum at pH ~ 7.5 after which it again starts decreasing. MAB species comes into existence from pH ~ 7.0 and its concentration increases continuously in higher pH range.

Equilibria involved in above complexation are given in Schemes 1 and 2

Scheme 1. Simultaneous complexation equilibria for M^{II} -Glygly-DOPA system.

Fig. 3. Speciation curves for (a) Ni^{II}-Glygly-Tyr, (b) Co^{II}-Glygly-Tyr and (c) Cd^{II}-Glygly-Tyr (1 : 1 : 1) Systems at 30 °C ($\mu = 0.10 M$ (NaNO₃)) : Curve (1) : [M]; (2) [MA]; (3) [MBH]; (4) [MB]; (5) [MABH]; (6) [MAB].

Experimental

The dipeptide and other ligands were of high purity and were used without further purification. All metal(II) nitrates used were extra pure Merck/Aldrich product. Solutions were prepared by standard method in CO₂ free double distilled water.

An Elico digital pH-meter model LI-127 with ATC probe and combined electrode type (CL-51B-Glass Body; range 0–14 pH unit; 0–100 °C automatic/manual) with accuracy ± 0.01 was used for pH measurements. The pH

Scheme 2. Simultaneous complexation equilibria for M^{II}-Glygly-Tyr.

(charges are omitted for the sake of simplicity)

meter was calibrated with aqueous buffers (pH 4.0 and 9.20) before and after titration.

Following sets of titration mixture were prepared by keeping total volume 50 mL and titrated against 0.10 M NaOH solution, ionic strengths ($\mu = 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 M$) is maintained by adding different concentration of NaNO₃ solution to each titration mixture at temperature 20 ± 1 °C and 30 ± 1 °C.

(i) Acid titration : HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)

(ii) Proton-ligand 'A' system : HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand 'A' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)

(iii) Proton-ligand 'B' system : HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand 'B' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)

(iv) Metal-ligand 'A' (1 : 1) binary system : HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal nitrate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) ligand 'A' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)

(v) Metal-ligand 'B' (1 : 1) binary system : HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal nitrate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) ligand 'B' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)

(iv) Metal-ligand 'A'-ligand 'B' (1 : 1 : 1) ternary system : HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal nitrate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) ligand 'A' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand 'B' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)

where, ligand 'A' = Glygly and ligand 'B' = DOPA/Tyr.

Note

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